

Damage Prediction In Quasi-statically Indented Sandwich Composite Structures Using A Two-region Plate Model

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Abstract

A model is developed for predicting indentation depth, diameter and planar delamination area for thin face sheet, honeycomb core sandwich composites subject to quasi-static indentation loading. The model is primarily based on the Ritz method of energy minimization. Nonlinear plate theory is utilized, and energy contributions from face sheet bending and membrane stresses are therefore accounted for, as are the contributions from both elastic and inelastic core deformations during loading and unloading. Further, the face sheet is divided into two regions, an inner region that is delaminated and an outer region that is intact. Model predictions are validated by comparison with experimental results for four different quasi-static indentation geometries, all of which consider sandwich plates with eight ply carbon/epoxy, quasi-isotropic face sheets and aluminum honeycomb cores. Geometrical variations are obtained by varying the core density, thickness and indenter diameter. It is shown that the model closely recreates the experimentally observed load versus displacement response and residual dent depth. Residual dent diameter and delamination diameter are generally slightly over-predicted.

Model Development

Figure 2: Boundaries with the two-region plate model.

Figure 3: Different modeling regimes in sandwich loading-unloading process.

For the symbols representing the boundaries in Figure 2, b is the indenter-face sheet contact boundary; c is the face sheet internal damage (delaminations/matrix crack) boundary; a is the intact region boundary.

Modeling Regime I:

- Uses engineering mechanics based solution of an isotropic plate on an elastic foundation [1, 2].

Modeling Regimes II and III:

- Utilizes the Ritz method of energy minimization based on the two-region plate model.
- Uses a single kinematically admissible displacement field for the entire deformed region.
- Considers the total strain energy Π as a sum of face sheet bending energy U_b , face sheet membrane energy U_m , and external work, V , done by the applied load and core resistance.

$$\Pi = U_b + U_m - V$$

- The total strain energy is minimized with respect to maximum face sheet deflection, w_o , external dent radius, a , and delamination radius, c and these parameters are then solved for numerically.

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial w_o} = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial a} = \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial c} = 0$$

quasi-static indentation force

Figure 1: Geometry considered.

Results

Figure 4: Model versus experimental load-displacement plot comparisons.

- Model closely recreates experimental load versus displacement response and residual dent depth.
- The overall mechanistic behavior of sandwich response to indentation loading captured better in the two-region plate model in comparison to the earlier model by Singh et al. [2].

Table 1: Model and experimental peak displacement and residual dent depth results.

Core Type	Indenter Size, mm	Peak Displacement, mm		Residual Dent Depth, mm	
		Model	Experimental	Model	Experimental
C1	25.4	1.32	1.34	0.55	0.50
C2	25.4	1.26	1.32	0.53	0.47
C3	25.4	1.33	1.34	0.44	0.53
C1	76.2	2.40	2.49	1.20	1.04

Table 2: Model and experimental dent and planar delamination radius results.

Core Type	Indenter Size, mm	Dent Radius, mm		Planar Delamination Radius, mm	
		Model	Experimental	Model	Experimental
C1	25.4	23.4	18.4	15.1	7.9
C2	25.4	22.2	17.0	14.7	9.8
C3	25.4	17.8	16.0	11.9	10.6
C1	76.2	33.3	29.0	19.9	Not Available

Conclusions

- The two-region plate model is able to predict loading-unloading response as well as residual dent diameter, dent depth and planar delamination radius.
- The model closely recreates the load versus displacement response and residual dent depth. Dent and planar delamination radius are over-predicted slightly.

References

1. R. Olsson, Engineering method for prediction of impact response and damage in sandwich panels, *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials*, 4, 2002, pp. 3-29.
2. A.K. Singh, B.D. Davidson, A.T. Zehnder and B.P.J. Hasseldine, An analytical model for the response of carbon/epoxy-aluminum honeycomb core sandwich structures under quasi-static indentation loading, *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials*, First Published November 9, 2017 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1099636217738709>).